

Afrotropical Asilidae (Diptera) 3*. The tribe Stichopogonini

by

J. G. H. Londt

(Natal Museum, Pietermaritzburg, South Africa)

SYNOPSIS

Species of the four genera comprising the Afrotropical Stichopogonini (*Stichopogon*, *Clinopogon*, *Psilinus* and *Sporadothrix*) are discussed. Two new species of *Stichopogon* (*S. irwini* from Natal, South Africa and *S. moremiensis* from Botswana and Rhodesia) are described, illustrated and compared with other Afrotropical species. Keys to genera and species are supplied.

INTRODUCTION

Four genera of the tribe Stichopogonini are known from the Afrotropical Region. These are *Stichopogon* Loew, 1847, *Clinopogon* Bezzi, 1910, *Psilinus* Wulp, 1899 and *Sporadothrix*, Hermann, 1908. They are characterised by the possession of eyes which are very much more widely separated at the vertex than at the level of the antennae; a completely developed prosternum; a stout third antennal segment bearing a short style, and an open marginal cell in the wings. These robber flies are usually sparsely setose and dusty-grey or sandy-yellow. The mystax is often fan-shaped and held in a roof-like manner above the rostrum.

Papavero (1973) suggested the possible synonymy of *Sporadothrix* with *Anypodetus* which he placed in his new subfamily Laphystiinae and placed the other three genera here considered as Stichopogonini in his new subfamily Stenopogoninae. Oldroyd (1974) on the other hand preferred to maintain the use of the older tribal classification in which all four genera are together in the tribe Stichopogonini, and I have followed him; which does not necessarily mean that I disagree with Papavero's interpretation. The use of the tribal classification is convenient as much of the work done on Afrotropical Asilidae has been done by Oldroyd and other workers who have used this system. On the matter of the possible synonymy of *Sporadothrix* with *Anypodetus* I believe that the fact that both these genera lack pulvilli is really not sufficient grounds. Until more material is available and detailed studies of genitalia have been done I prefer to retain *Sporadothrix*.

The present study was based entirely on material housed in southern African museums: Natal Museum (N.M.), Pietermaritzburg, now incorporating Diptera previously housed in the Transvaal Museum, Pretoria; South African Museum (S.A.M.), Cape Town; Albany Museum (A.M.), Grahamstown; Durban Museum and Art Gallery (D.M.), Durban; State Museum (S.M.), Windhoek, South West Africa; National Museum of Rhodesia (N.M.R.), Bulawayo; Museum of the Plant Protection Research Institute (P.P.R.I.), Salisbury, Rhodesia. As these collections contain very little material from countries north of southern Africa infor-

* Part 1 & 2—*Ann. Natal Mus.* 23(1): 43-55 (1977); 23(2): 419-428 (1978).

Fig. 1. *Psilinus cinerascens*, a fairly typical example of the tribe Stichopogonini.

mation pertaining to distribution outside of this subregion is obviously very limited.

Key to the genera of Afrotropical Stichopogonini (adults)
(Modified after Oldroyd, 1963)

- 1. Pulvilli present, even if much reduced..... 2
- Pulvilli absent..... **Sporadothrix** Hermann
- 2. Pulvilli reduced to narrow vestiges about one-third the length of the claws; eyes separated at vertex by about three times the width of ocellar tubercle .
Psilinus Wulp
- Pulvilli normal, about as long as the claws; eyes separated at vertex by about four or more times the width of ocellar tubercle 3
- 3. Fourth posterior cell of wing with a long stalk at its base; a pair of well-developed ocellar bristles present; tiny flies, less than 10 mm in length **Stichopogon** Loew
- Fourth posterior cell of wing without a stalk at its base; a number of small insignificant ocellar bristles may be present; larger more robust flies, greater than 10 mm in length **Clinopogon** Bezzi

Genus *Stichopogon* Loew, 1847Key to Afrotropical species of *Stichopogon* (adults)

1. Femora mostly pale yellow-brown 2
- Femora mostly dark red-brown 3
2. ♂ genitalia (Fig. 26) with elongate epandrium and gonocoxites; style straight; five proctigal spines in each group; ♀ subgenital plate (Fig. 34) with a distal tuft of golden setae **hermanni** Bezzi
- ♂ genitalia (Fig. 23) not elongate; style with a slight upward curve; four proctigal spines in each group; ♀ (Fig. 31) subgenital plate without a distal tuft of golden setae **irwini** sp. n.
3. Legs entirely black **unicolor** Ricardo
- Legs not entirely black 4
4. Mesonotum with a distinctive pattern of shiny-black markings; tibia black, tarsus contrastingly yellowish **umkomaasensis** Oldroyd
- Mesonotum without shiny-black markings; tibia not entirely black 5
5. Grey bands of abdomen not well-developed and more or less equal on all segments (Fig. 14); ♂ (Fig. 22) with short genitalia, style strongly upturned; proctigal spines as curved combs; ♀ (Fig. 30) with tergum VIII bare and shiny laterally; subgenital plate without a distal tuft of golden setae **caffer** Hermann
- Grey bands well-developed and not equal on all segments; ♂ with elongate genitalia; style more or less straight; ♀ subgenital plate with a distal tuft of golden setae 6
6. ♂ with conspicuous darkly pigmented wing spot at fork of R_{4+5} , and first posterior cell shortish (Fig. 6); ♀ with no, or only a trace of a, wing spot **punctum** Loew
- ♂ without a wing spot. First posterior cell more elongate (Figs 7, 12) 7
7. Malagasy subregion. ♂ genitalia as Fig. 29 **parvulus** (Bigot)
- African mainland. ♂ genitalia as Fig. 28 **moremiensis** sp. n.

Stichopogon caffer Hermann, 1907 (Figs 14, 22, 30)

Stichopogon caffer Hermann, 1907. *Z. Syst. Hymen. Dipt.* 7: 3-4.

Redescription: ♂: Shape of eyes, face and vertex similar to *S. punctum* (Fig. 2). Antenna uniform dark red-brown. Face dark red-brown, gold pruinose, with a few moderately well-developed shiny-yellow setae. Mystax as a tightly-packed fan of shiny-yellow bristles. Vertex dark red-brown, fine red-gold pruinose and bearing fine yellow setae. Occiput dark red-brown, silver pruinose, stout dorsal setae yellow, numerous ventral setae fine silver-white. Rostrum shiny dark red-brown.

Thorax: Laterally dark red-brown, yellow-gold pruinose, humeri shiny-amber. Dorsally dark red-brown, fine red-gold pruinose. Setae: 1 presutural, 1 supra-alar, 2 postalar, dorsocentrals and acrostichals not clearly defined. Numerous fine setae on margin of scutellum. Wing membrane hyaline and iridescent, veins dark red-brown. Legs: Coxa, trochanter and femur dark red-brown, silver pruinose,

bearing fine silver-white setae; tibia orange-brown with distal half dark red-brown; tarsus dark red-brown; all bristles yellow. Claws dark red-brown, empodium orange-brown; pulvilli light yellow-brown.

Abdomen: Dark red-brown, fine red-gold pruinose. Tergal pattern as in ♀. ♂ genital structure as in Fig. 22. Epandrium and gonocoxites relatively short; style distinctly upturned; proctigal comb made up of more than ten spines arranged as a curved band.

♀: Similar to ♂; ♀ genitalia as in Fig. 30. Subgenital plate shiny dark red-brown and lacking a distal tuft of gold setae; lateral aspects of tergum VIII shiny dark red-brown. Tergal pattern as in Fig. 14.

Material examined: SOUTH AFRICA: *Transvaal:* 2 ♂ 1 ♀, Malelane, II.1915, Roberts (N.M.); 2 ♀, Pretoria, 10.III.1916, Swierstra (N.M.); 1 ♀, Kruger National Park (K.N.P.), Lower Sabie Camp area, open savanna and riverbanks, Stuckenberg (N.M.); 1 ♀, K.N.P., Pafuri, 29.XI.1973, Van Reenen (N.M.); 1 ♀, K.N.P., Satara, 26.IV–1.V.1969, Potgieter & Strydom (N.M.); 1 ♀, Koppie Alleen, 25.XII.1963, (N.M.); 4 ♂ 7 ♀, K.N.P., Timbetene Tswini Waterholes, savanna woodland near Skukuza, 9.XII.1972, Stuckenberg (N.M.); 1 ♂, W.b (? Warmbaths), 6.I.1904 (N.M.). *Cape Province:* 1 ♂ 1 defective, near Douglas, 23.II.1961, Vári (N.M.); 1 ♀, Alexandria Forest, 27.II.1969, Gess (A.M.); 1 ♀, Resolution, Grahamstown Dist., 1930, Walton (S.A.M.); 1 ♀, Heuningklip River, 25 km W. Queenstown, 27.X.1978, river bank, Londt & Miller (N.M.). *Natal:* 1 ♀, 10 miles N. Jozini, 28.XI.1971, Irwin, dry forest, 800 ft (N.M.); 1 ♀, 10 miles W. Charters Creek, St Lucia Game Reserve, 23.XI.1971, 4 m alt., Irwin (N.M.); 1 ♀, 20 miles S. Ndumu Game Reserve Camp, dry scrub forest, 320 ft, 29.XI.1971, Irwin (N.M.); 1 ♀, Ndumu Reserve, 1–10.XII.1963, Stuckenberg (N.M.); 2 ♀, 4 miles S. Ndumu Game Reserve Camp, 1.XII.1971, Irwin (N.M.); 9 ♂ 4 ♀, 15 km

Figs 2–5. Anterior aspect of head. 2. *Stichopogon punctum*. 3. *S. umkomaasensis*. 4. *S. unicolor*. 5. *Psilinus cinerascens*.

SE Ingwavuma, 21.II.1979, bushy area with big trees, Londt (N.M.); 1 ♂, Malvern, II.1953, Capener (N.M.). TRANSKEI: 4 ♂ 9 ♀, Xuka River, 10 km E. Engcobo, 26.X.1978, river bank, Londt & Miller (N.M.); 1 ♂ 1 ♀, Glen Grey Falls on Wit-Kei River, 25 km N.E. Queenstown, 27.X.1978, above falls, Miller & Londt (N.M.). LESOTHO: 1 ♀, Orange River, near Quthing, I.1963, Stuckenberg (N.M.); 1 ♂, Mamathes, 3.III.1951, Jacot-Guillarmod (A.M.). SOUTH WEST AFRICA: 2 ♂, Takuasa, Kavango 14–19.VIII.1971, Channing, Penrith & Coetzee (S.M.); 1 ♀, Oruwanje, 27.XI.1970, Zinn (S.M.); 1 ♀ Hoffnung 66, Windhoek, 3.II.1971, Penrith & Harding (S.M.); 1 ♀ Otjikoko-Sud 61, Omaruru, 10–13.II.1972, Coetzee (S.M.); 1 ♀, Mafa, II.1923, Mus. Exped. (S.A.M.); 1 ♀, Tsumeb, XII.1919, Tucker (S.A.M.). MOZAMBIQUE: 1 ♀, Luabo, Lower Zambezi River, IV.1958, Usher (N.M.). RHODESIA: 1 ♂ 1 ♀, Base Camp, Chikwarawara, Chipese (Tribal Trust Land), 11.XII.1974, De Moor (N.M.R.); 1 ♀, Marandellas, II.1963, (N.M.R.); 1 ♂, Turk Mine, 10.XI.1957 (N.M.R.); 1 ♀, Gatooma, I.1928, Cuthbertson (P.P.R.I.); 1 ♀, Bulawayo, 13.IX.1923, Stevenson (S.A.M.). BOTSWANA: 3 ♂, Nata, 13–15.I.1978, at light, Holm, Jacobs, Kirsten & Scholtz (N.M.).

Distribution: A widespread species apparently associated with savanna woodland areas near water. Activity period summarised in Table 1.

Stichopogon hermanni Bezzi, 1910 (Figs 13, 15, 26, 34)

Stichopogon hermanni Bezzi, 1910, *Ann. Mus. nat. Hung.* 8: 145.

Stichopogon engeli Lindner, 1973, *S.W.A. Wissen. Gesell.* 27: 76–77. *syn. n.*

Stichopogon maculipennis Engel & Cuthbertson, 1939, *J. ent. Soc. sth. Afr.* 2: 188. *syn. n.*

Redescription: ♂: *Head:* Shape of eyes, and vertex similar to *S. punctum*. Antennae uniformly dark red-brown. Face dark red-brown masked by silver pruinescence, bears a few fine shiny-silver setae. Mystax composed of a fan of shiny pale-yellow setae. Vertex dark red-brown, fine orange-gold pruinose except for a region of silver pruinescence just above antennal bases. Occiput dark red-brown masked by silver pruinescence, stout dorsal setae yellow, numerous ventral setae shiny silver-white. Rostrum shiny dark red-brown.

Thorax: Laterally dark red-brown, silver pruinose (some specimens are much lighter in colour being light orange-brown). Dorsally dark red-brown, fine orange-gold pruinose. Setae: 1 presutural, 1 supra-alar, 1 postalar, dorsocentrals and acrostichals not clearly defined. Margin of scutellum with a few fine vertical setae. Wing membrane hyaline and iridescent, veins light yellow-brown. Legs: Coxae like thorax, remainder uniform light orange-brown, fifth tarsal segment may be darker brown. Claws dark red-brown distally and orange-brown basally, pulvilli pale-yellow, empodium and all leg bristles pale-yellow, fine setae shiny silver-yellow.

Abdomen: Dark brown, uniformly orange-gold pruinose masking background colour. Tergal pattern as for ♀. ♂ genital structure as in Fig. 26. Epandrium and gonocoxites elongate; style straight; each proctigal comb made up of five spines in a straight row.

♀: Similar to ♂; ♀ genitalia as in Fig. 34. Subgenital plate bears a distal tuft of gold setae. Tergal pattern as in Fig. 15.

Figs 6-13. *Stichopogon* wings. 6. entire wing of male *S. punctum*. 7. entire wing of male *S. parvulus*. 8-11. variations in the wing tip of male *S. punctum*. 12. wing tip of male *S. moremiensis*. 13. wing tip of male *S. hermanni*.

Material examined: SOUTH AFRICA: *Cape Province*: 2 ♀, 16 miles E. Cradock, farm 'Who can tell', 11.III.1972, 1 000 m, Irwin (N.M.); 1 ♂ 3 ♀, Willowmore, ♀-1.XI.1906 ♀-1.XI.1912 ♂-15.XII.1915 ♀-25.III.1920, Brauns (N.M.); 5 ♀, Malmesbury, 4 ♀-5.XII.1926 1 ♀-XII.1925 (N.M.); 1 ♂ 1 ♀, Knersvlakte, N. Van Rhynsdorp, 6-9.X.1964, Stuckenberg (N.M.); 1 ♂, Brandkop Area, Calvinia Dist., 14.X.1964, Stuckenberg (N.M.); 1 ♂, Nuweveld Escarpment, Rietvlei, I.1949, Mus. Exped. (S.A.M.); 1 ♂, O'Okiep (?) (S.A.M.); 1 ♀, Buffels River, Ladismith Dist., X.1937 (S.A.M.); 1 ♀, Middelburg Dist., XI.1935, Mus. Exped. (S.A.M.); 1 ♀, Meirings Poort, X.1937 (S.A.M.); 1 ♂, Beaufort West Dist., II.1958, Mus. Exped. (S.A.M.); 1 ♂ 1 ♀, 18 m. E. Touws R. to Hondewater, XII.1962 (S.A.M.); 1 ♀, Ceres Dist., Matroosberg, 3 500 ft, I.1917, Lightfoot (S.A.M.). 2 ♂ 7 ♀, Heuningklip River, 25 km W. Queenstown, 27.X.1978, river bank, Londt & Miller (N.M.); 7 ♂ 11 ♀, Cradock, Fish River bank, 28.X.1978, Londt & Miller (N.M.); 1 ♂ 2 ♀, Klein-Vis River, 32 km N.W. Somerset East, 28.X.1978, river banks, Miller & Londt (N.M.); 2 ♂ 3 ♀, Groot River, 7 km N. Steytlerville, 30.X.1978, river banks, Londt & Miller (N.M.); 1 ♀, 10 km E. Rhodes, rocky river banks, 9.I.1979, Londt & Stuckenberg (N.M.); 2 ♀, Rhodes, rocky river banks, 10-11.I.1979, Londt & Stuckenberg (N.M.). *Orange Free State*: 1 ♀, Caledon River between Bethulie & Aliwal North, X.1935, Mus. Exped. (S.A.M.); TRANSKEI: 4 ♂ 15 ♀, Glen Grey Falls on Wit-Kei River, 25 km N.E. Queenstown, 27.X.1978, above falls, Miller & Londt (N.M.); 1 ♀, Telle River, sandy banks, 10.I.1979, Stuckenberg & Londt (N.M.); 1 ♀, Dangerhoek on Telle River, 10.I.1979, (with prey Diptera: Ephydriidae), Londt & Stuckenberg (N.M.). SOUTH WEST AFRICA: 2 ♂ 8 ♀, Kuiseb River at Gobabeb, 800 m, Riverine forest and sand, 12.II.1974, Irwin (N.M.); 4 ♀, Maltahöhe Dist., Aandster farm, 1 000 m, Vegetated dune and grassland, 16.II.1974, Irwin (N.M.); 2 ♂ 3 ♀, Keetmanshoop Dist., Narubis near Löwen River, riverine forest, 870 m, 20.II.1974, Irwin (N.M.); 2 ♀, Omaruru Dist., Omaruru, dry wash in *Acacia* covered plain, 1 200 m, 5.II.1974, Irwin (N.M.); 3 ♂ 7 ♀, S.E. corner of Namib

Desert Park, near Knamhoek farm, Vegetated moving dune, 860 m, 15.II.1974, Irwin (N.M.); 1 ♀, Keetmanshoop Dist., 17,5 km N. Grünau, dry river bed, 1 350 m, 30.I.1974, Irwin (N.M.); 1 ♀, Bethanien Dist., 15 km W. Goageb, sandy river bed, 1 100 m, 19.II.1974, Irwin (N.M.); 3 ♂ 12 ♀, Damaraland, near Rooipoort farm at Ugab River, sandy river bottom, 600 m, 6.II.1974, Irwin (N.M.); 4 ♂ 1 ♀, Keetmanshoop Dist., 75 km S. Keetmanshoop, Guigatsis River, Vegetated dunes, 1 120 m, 30.I.1974, Irwin (N.M.); 2 ♂ 9 ♀, Otjinungwa, 17-22.XI.1970, Kensley & Penrith (S.M.); 1 ♀, Sesriem 137, Maltahöhe, 15-17.II.1973, Penrith & Tebje (S.M.). RHODESIA: 1 ♂ 3 ♀, Kariba Gorge, Urunwe, ♂-30.VIII.1938 (with tiny nymph Acrididae) ♀-14.IX.1938 (with tiny nymph Dictyopharidae) 2 ♀-30.VIII.1938 (with tiny nymphs of Acrididae), Williams (P.P.R.I.); 2 ♂ 1 ♀, Kariba Gorge, ♂-26.VII.1938 2 ♀-9.VIII.1938, Clarkson (P.P.R.I.). These Rhodesian specimens are paratypes of *S. maculipennis*.

Distribution: A species of arid areas spreading from South West Africa northwards into Rhodesia (Zambezi Valley) and southwards into the south-western parts of the Cape Province. Activity period summarised in Table 1.

TABLE 1.

A summary of the seasonal incidence of Afrotropical Stichopogonini as derived from collecting data of specimens listed in this contribution.

Species	Months of collection											
	J	A	S	O	N	D	J	F	M	A	M	J
<i>Stichopogon caffer</i>			•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	
<i>S. hermanni</i>	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•			
<i>S. irwini</i>						•						
<i>S. moremiensis</i>			•	•								
<i>S. parvulus</i>						•		•				
<i>S. punctum</i>		•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•		
<i>S. umkomaasensis</i>						•		•				
<i>S. unicolor</i>		•	•				•					•
<i>Psilinus cinerascens</i>							•					
<i>Clinopogon nicobarensis</i>						•		•	•	•		

Remarks: The holotype and allotype of *S. maculipennis* are not to be found in the National Museum, Bulawayo, as stated by Engel & Cuthbertson (1939) but I have studied some of the paratypes housed at the Plant Protection Research Institute in Salisbury. These specimens do not bear paratype labels and in some instances are labelled '? *S. hermanni*'. Although these specimens show the brownish wing marking mentioned by both Engel & Cuthbertson (1939) and Oldroyd (1974) there is some variation in the intensity of this marking. The genitalia of both males and females approach very closely those of other specimens identified as *S. hermanni*. The epandrium of the Rhodesian males is not quite as elongate as shown in the illustrated male but as there is a degree of

variation in this character I do not wish to place any emphasis on this slight difference. The style also shows slight differences in that the Rhodesian males have slightly larger styli with a somewhat more prominent terminal section. These slight differences may be due to individual and geographic variation and so for the present I regard *S. maculipennis* as a synonym of *S. hermanni*.

S. engeli was described from a single male from Gobabeb, South West Africa. I have seen a number of specimens from this locality and although the holotype, which I have not seen, is a little smaller than most of the examples that I have studied, Lindner's description indicates that the specimen belongs to the widely spread *S. hermanni* which has been collected from many localities in South West Africa. I therefore consider *S. engeli* as yet another synonym of *S. hermanni*.

***Stichopogon irwini* sp. n. (Figs 16, 23, 31)**

Description (Based on 2 ♂ 1 ♀ pinned): **Holotype ♂: Head:** Shape of eyes, face and vertex similar to *S. punctum*. Scape and pedicel orange-brown, third antennal segment orange-brown with dark-brown base, spine-tipped style dark-brown. Face gold pruinose equipped with four moderately-developed shiny-yellow setae. Mystax like a tightly-packed fan of shiny yellow-gold bristles. Vertex dull-blackish covered with shiny-gold pruinescence and micro-setae. Occiput dull-black, gold pruinose dorsally, silver pruinose ventrally. Lower occiput equipped with shortish silver setae. Rostrum dark shiny red-brown.

Thorax: Laterally dull dark red-brown with patches of silver pruinescence and setae. Halteres light yellow-white apically, dull yellow-brown basally. Dorsally dull dark red-brown with patches of gold pruinescence. Setae: 1 presutural, 1 supra-alar, 1 postalar, 2 weakish dorsocentrals at hind margin of mesonotum, numerous fine setae on margin of scutellum. Wing membrane hyaline and iridescent, veins dark-brown except for bases of main veins which are yellow-brown. Legs: Coxae yellow-brown with darker patches adjacent to thorax; femora and tibiae light yellow-brown; tarsi light reddish-brown, the terminal segment a little darker than others; claws dark red-brown with lighter base; pulvilli yellowish and almost as long as claws, empodium light-yellowish, as long as claws. Leg setae light-yellow on femora and tibiae and brown on tarsal segments.

Figs 14–21. Diagrammatic representations of abdominal colour patterns in *Stichopogon*. 14. *S. caffer*. 15. *S. hermanni*. 16. *S. irwini*. 17. *S. moremiensis*. 18. *S. parvulus*. 19. *S. punctum*. 20. *S. umkomaasensis*. 21. *S. unicolor*.

Abdomen: Orange-brown with darker brown patches dorsally. Pattern of silver-gold tergal pruinescence as in ♀. ♂ genital structure as in Fig. 23, similar to *S. caffer*. Empodium short without prominent posterolateral lobes. Proctigal combs not arranged as a curved row of spines as in *S. caffer* but consisting of groups of only four spines arranged in straight rows either side of the proctiger. Gonocoxites and styles have a different shape to those of *S. caffer*; styles are not so markedly upturned distally.

Paratypes: 1 ♂ 1 ♀. Agree well with description of holotype. ♀ genitalia as in Fig. 31, very similar to *S. caffer*. Distal part of subgenital plate not as sharply pointed as in *S. caffer* but this slight difference may not be significant. Tergal pattern as in Fig. 16.

Material examined: 1 ♂ holotype, 1 ♂ 1 ♀ paratypes, SOUTH AFRICA: Natal: 4 miles S. Ndumu Game Reserve Camp, dry scrub forest, 160 ft, 1.XII.1971. M. E. & B. J. Irwin. Natal Museum type number 2226.

Distribution: Known only from the type locality.

Remarks: The specimens used in the description of this species were previously studied by the late Mr H. Oldroyd and identified by him as *S. hermanni*. This identification appears to have been based largely on the pale coloured legs. The genitalic structure of both male and female, however, places these specimens nearer to *S. caffer* than to *S. hermanni*. The females of *S. caffer* and *S. irwini* both lack a setal tuft on the subgenital plate while the males have shortish epandria and upturned styli. (In this respect the males have an affinity to two other closely related species—*S. umkomaasensis* and *S. unicolor*.) I have pleasure in naming this species after Dr M. E. Irwin and his wife who have been instrumental in collecting many fine asilid specimens in southern Africa.

***Stichopogon moremiensis* sp. n. (Figs 12, 17, 28, 36)**

Description (Based on 5 ♂ 8 ♀ pinned): Holotype ♂: *Head*: Shape of eyes, face and vertex similar to *S. punctum*. Antennae blackish, fine gold pruinose. Face blackish, silver pruinose, bearing a few fine silver-white setae. Mystax shiny yellow-white. Vertex dull-blackish and orange-gold pruinose. Occiput dull-blackish covered with silver pruinescence and short silver setae. Rostrum dark shiny red-brown.

Thorax: Laterally dull-black and uniformly silver pruinose. Halteres light-yellow apically, dull yellow-brown basally. Dorsally shiny dark brown-black, fine gold pruinose especially in region of tegulae. Setae: 1 presutural, other setae not evident; a few fine setae on margin of scutellum. Wing membrane hyaline and iridescent, veins light-brown, except for bases of main veins which are yellowish. Legs: coxae, trochanters and femora dark red-brown, silver pruinose; tibiae dark red-brown distally, yellow-brown proximally; tarsi, claws and empodium dark red-brown, pulvilli dull yellow-brown.

Abdomen: Dark brown-black with patches of silver pruinescence as in ♀. Genitalia very similar to *S. parvulus* but shape of epandrium, gonocoxites, aedeagus and style as in Fig. 28.

Figs 22–29. Lateral aspect of male genitalia. 22. *S. caffer*. 23. *S. irwini*. 24. *S. umkomaasensis*. 25. *S. unicolor*. 26. *S. hermanni*. 27. *S. punctum*. 28. *S. moremiensis*. 29. *S. parvulus*.

Paratypes: 4 ♂ 8 ♀. Agree well with holotype. ♀ abdominal pattern as Fig. 17. ♀ genitalia as Fig. 36, similar to *S. parvulus*, *S. punctum*, and *S. hermanni*.

Material examined: BOTSWANA: 1 ♂ holotype, 1 ♂ 3 ♀ paratypes, Mboma Island, Moremi Reserve, in thin *Acacia nigrescens* and *Hyperrhaenia* grassland, IX.1977, A. Russel-Smith; 2 ♂ 4 ♀ paratypes, same data, in grazed *Sporobolus* grass, 19.IX.1977; 1 ♂ paratype, same date, in sparse *Acacia nigrescens* woodland on game tracks, sandy soil, 12.IX.1977; 1 ♀ paratype, same data, water trap, *Sporobolus*, 16.X.1977. All types in Natal Museum NM2227.

Additional Material: RHODESIA: 3 ♂, Khami, 1.X.1938 (N.M.R.).

Distribution: Presently known only from the Moremi Reserve, N.W. Botswana, and Khami (Khami Ruins, S.E. Bulawayo), Rhodesia.

Remarks: *S. moremiensis* most closely resembles the Madagascar species *S. parvulus*. The male and female genitalia also have strong similarities to *S. punctum* and *S. hermanni*. Although this new species may eventually prove to be the same as *S. parvulus* for the present I recognise it as a distinct species.

Stichopogon parvulus (Bigot, 1859) (Figs 7, 18, 29, 37)

Isopogon parvulus Bigot, 1859. *Ann. Soc. ent. France* (3)7: 424.

Leptarthrus parvulus; Hull, 1962 *Robber Flies of the World* p. 41.

Stichopogon parvulus; Oldroyd, 1959. *Mém. Ins. Sc. Madagascar* 11: 268.

Stichopogon parvulus, originally described as an *Isopogon* Loew (misspelt *Ysopogon* by Oldroyd, 1959) was transferred to *Leptarthrus* Stephens when *Isopogon* was synonymised with this genus (Hull, 1962). Oldroyd (1959) correctly placed the species in *Stichopogon*.

Redescription: ♂: *Head*: Shape of face, eyes and vertex similar to *S. punctum*. Antennae blackish with silver pruinescence. Face probably blackish but masked by a dense silver-grey pruinescence, bears a few moderately well-developed white downturned setae. Mystax like a tightly-packed fan of shiny-white bristles. Vertex blackish covered with orange-gold pruinescence. Occiput black, covered with dense silver-grey pruinescence, occipital bristles light yellow-brown.

Thorax: Blackish, silver-grey pruinose laterally, orange-gold pruinose dorsally. Setae: 1 presutural, 1 supra-alar, 1 postalar, all orange-brown. Wings hyaline and iridescent. Legs: Coxa, trochanter femur and distal half of tibia dark red-brown. Proximal end of hind femur may be orange-brown. Proximal half of tibia and tarsal segments predominantly orange-brown. Claws dark-brown with light red-brown base. Empodium brown. Pulvilli light orange-brown. All leg bristles and setae light-yellow to orange-brown.

Abdomen: Dark orange-brown with patches of silver and gold pruinescence, pattern as in ♀. ♂ genitalia as in Fig. 29. Epandrium long with well-developed postero-lateral lobes. Gonopods with undulating upper margin (in lateral view); styli jut straight out distally and have characteristic downturned tips.

♀: Similar to ♂. ♀ genitalia as in Fig. 37; subgenital plate has terminal tufts of gold setae as in *S. punctum*. Tergal pattern as in Fig. 18.

Material examined: MADAGASCAR: 1 ♂ 5 ♀, Sainte-Luce, 10 m, dct. Fort Dauphin, 22–24.II.1958, Stuckenberg (N.M.); 3 ♂ 4 ♀, Station Agric. Alaotra,

Figs 30-37. Lateral aspect of female genitalia. 30. *S. caffer*. 31. *S. irvini*. 32. *S. umkomaasensis*. 33. *S. unicolor*. 34. *S. hermanni*. 35. *S. punctum*. 36. *S. moremiensis*. 37. *S. parvulus*.

800 m, dct. Ambatondrazaka, 24.XII.1957, Stuckenberg (N.M.); 1 ♂ 3 ♀, Route d'Anosibe, 840 m, dct. Moramanga, 18–24.XII.1957, Stuckenberg (N.M.); 2 ♂ 1 ♀, Sept-Lacs, 100 m, dct. Tuléar, 13–16.II.1958, Stuckenberg (N.M.); 1 ♀, Ranomafana, XII.1955, Stuckenberg (N.M.).

Distribution: Known only from Madagascar. Activity period summarised in Table 1.

Remarks: *S. parvulus* has much in common with *S. moremiensis* and although a number of small differences are evident the two species may eventually prove to be the same.

Stichopogon punctum Loew, 1851 (Figs 2, 6, 8–11, 19, 27, 35)

Stichopogon punctum Loew, 1851. *Progr. Realschule Meseritz*, p. 15.

Stichopogon punctatus; Loew, 1852. *Ber. Verh. K. Preuss. Akad. Wiss.* 1852: 658.

Redescription: ♂: *Head:* Shape of eyes, face and vertex as in Fig. 2. Antennae blackish, fine silver pruinose. Face blackish, mainly silver pruinose but centre may be orange-gold pruinose, bears a few shiny yellow-white bristles. Vertex blackish, orange-gold pruinose. Occiput blackish, orange-gold and silver pruinose covered ventrally with short shiny fine white setae.

Thorax: Laterally dull-blackish, uniformly orange-gold pruinose. Halteres yellow-white with slightly darker base. Dorsally shiny-black, covered with fine gold pruinescence and short shiny-yellow setae. Setae: 1 presutural, 1 supra-alar, 1 postalar all shiny light-yellow. Wing membrane hyaline and iridescent, possesses a small very distinct dark chitinous spot at the fork of R_{4+5} . The size and shape of this spot is somewhat variable (Figs 6, 8–11). Wing membrane along distal margin has a diffuse brownish patch stretching from R_1 to R_4 (Fig. 6) and appears to be due to a concentration of microtrichia in this area. R_4 is shorter and more strongly curved than in other *Stichopogon* species (compare Figs 6 & 7). Legs: Coxae, trochanters and femora blackish, silver pruinose. Tibiae and tarsal segments orange-brown with dark-brown apices. Claws blackish; pulvilli well-developed, light-brown. Empodium and bristles of legs light-brown.

Abdomen: Shiny dark brown-black with patches of silver and gold pruinescence in a pattern similar to ♀. Covered with moderately long silver and orange-gold setae. ♂ genitalia as in Fig. 27. Epandrium long with well-developed posterolateral lobes. Proctigal comb as in *S. hermanni*. Gonopods fairly elongate with smoothly rounded upper margin (in lateral view). Style gently curved upwards distally and jutting out in a similar manner to *S. parvulus*, *S. moremiensis* and *S. hermanni*.

♀: Similar to ♂ but usually without the characteristic wing spot although the wing may have a rather buckled appearance at the fork of R_{4+5} , and a trace of a wing spot may be evident. ♀ abdominal pattern as in Fig. 19 and genitalia as in Fig. 35. Subgenital plate bears a well-developed tuft of shiny-gold setae.

Material examined: SOUTH AFRICA: *Transvaal:* 3 ♂ 1 ♀, Pretoria, 20.XI.1915 Swierstra (N.M.); 1 ♀, Pretoria, 25.X.1947, Van Son (N.M.); 3 ♂ 3 ♀, Noordkaap River at Barberton–Nelspruit Road, riverbank bushveld, 7.XI.1970, Stuckenberg (N.M.); 3 ♂ 3 ♀, Kruger National Park, Olifants River near Balule, riparian

woodland, 9.XII.1972, Stuckenberg (N.M.); 1 ♀, Kruger National Park, Olifants River gorge, XII.1972, Stuckenberg (N.M.); 1 ♂ 1 ♀, Boekenhoutskloof, 30 km N.E. Pretoria, 24.IX.1977, Bernon (N.M.); 2 ♀, 75 km W. Messina, Greeppwald farm, 4-9.XI.1973, Van Reenen (N.M.); 1 ♂, Mosdene, Naboomspruit, 4.XII.1976 (N.M.R.); 1 ♂, Kaapmuiden, 30.X.1918, Tucker (S.A.M.); 5 ♂ 1 ♀, Ofcolaco, Selati River, 7-8.XII.1976, Miller (N.M.); 1 ♂, 7 km N. Hazyview, Sabie River, 6.XII.1976, Miller (N.M.). *Cape Province*: 1 ♀, Willowmore, 1.X.1921, Brauns (N.M.); 1 ♀ Grahamstown, 16.XII.1952, Stuckenberg (N.M.); 1 ♂, Grahamstown, 15.III.1959, Mc C. Callan (A.M.); 2 ♀, 10 miles N. Pella, sandy bank of Orange River, 940 ft, 4.IX.1972, Irwin (N.M.); 3 ♂ 3 ♀, Klein-Vis River, 8 km W. Somerset East, 29.X.1978, river banks, Miller & Londt (N.M.). *Natal*: 3 ♂ 1 ♀, Ndumu Game Reserve, Ingwavuma District, 1-10.XI.1963, Stuckenberg (N.M.); 2 ♀, Dukuduku Forest, 4 miles W. St Lucia, 3 m, 26.XI.1971, Irwin (N.M.); 2 ♂ 1 ♀, 10 miles W. Charters Creek, St Lucia Game Reserve, 4 m, 23.XI.1971, Irwin (N.M.); 2 ♂ 2 ♀ 1 defective, Cape Vidal, 20 miles N. St Lucia, coastal dune forest, 0-20 m, 24.XI.1971, Irwin (N.M.); 1 ♀, 10 miles N. Jozini, dry forest, 800 ft, 28.XI.1971, Irwin (N.M.); 4 ♂ 6 ♀, 20 km W. Tugela Ferry, ex. Malaise trap, 26-27.II.1977, Miller (N.M.); 9 ♂ 7 ♀, Mkuze Reserve, 300 m, 3-11.X.1977, Londt (N.M.); 1 ♂ 1 ♀, Pomeroy, 13.IV.1974, Irwin (N.M.); 1 ♂ 1 ♀, Valley of a Thousand Hills, Drummond, 17.X.1972, Irwin (N.M.); 1 ♀, Durban XII.1915, Marley (N.M.); 1 ♂, Stella Bush, Durban, II.1915, Marley (N.M.); 1 ♀, Congella, III.1915, Marley (N.M.); 1 ♂, Estcourt, 23.XII.1944, Marley (P.P.R.I.); 2 ♂, Umbilo, Durban, 3.XII.1936, Bevis (D.M.); 1 ♂, Doonside, 11.I.1917, Bevis (D.M.); 2 ♂ 1 ♀, Umbilo, Durban, 31.IX.1945, Marley (N.M.); 1 ♀, Umhlanga, 26.X.1941, Bevis (D.M.); 4 ♂ 5 ♀, Tugela Ferry, river banks, 18.II.1979, Londt (N.M.); 1 ♂, 4 km N. Tugela Ferry, near stream, 18.II.1979, Londt (N.M.) 3 ♀, 10 km W. Luneburg, stream bank, 19.II.1979, Londt (N.M.); 1 ♀, St. Lucia Estuary, forest path, 22.II.1979, Londt (N.M.); 2 ♀, Winkelspruit, on dunes near sea, 17.III.1979, Londt (N.M.). *TRANSKEI*: 1 ♂, Xuka River, 10 km E. Engcobo, 26.X.1978, river bank, Londt & Miller (N.M.); 5 ♂ 5 ♀, Cacadu River nr. Lady Frere, 27.X.1978, river banks, Londt & Miller (N.M.); 8 ♂ 11 ♀, 8 km W. Matatiele, Sandy river banks, 8.I.1979, Stuckenberg & Londt (N.M.); 1 ♂ 1 ♀, 22 km S.W. Matatiele, sandy river banks, 8.I.1979, Londt & Stuckenberg (N.M.); 1 ♂ 4 ♀, Telle River, sandy banks, 10.I.1979, Stuckenberg & Londt (N.M.); 4 ♂ 7 ♀, Luzi River, Pitseng Pass, sandy river banks, 12.I.1979, Londt & Stuckenberg (N.M.). *LESOTHO*: 1 ♀, Mamathes, with Diptera Lauxaniidae, 14.XI.1954, Jacot-Guillarmod (N.M.); 1 ♂ 1 ♀ 1 defective, Mamathes, 18.XI.1945, Bevis (D.M.); 1 ♀, same data, 21.XI.1945 (D.M.); 1 ♀, Mamathes, 25.XII.1947, Jacot-Guillarmod (A.M.); 1 ♂, same data, 20.XII.1947 (A.M.). *SOUTH WEST AFRICA*: 1 ♂, Ugab River Bridge, 29.II.1969, Lamoral (N.M.); 5 ♂ 1 ♀, Ugab River, sandy river bottom, 600 m, 6.II.1974, Irwin (N.M.); 5 ♂ 11 ♀ (1 ♀ with small Diptera-Tachinidae), Keetmanshoop Dist., Narubis near Löwen River, riverine forest, 870 m, 20.I.1974, Irwin (N.M.); 1 ♂, Bethanien dist., 45 km W. Seeheim, sandy river bank, 800 m, 19.II.1974, Irwin (N.M.); 3 ♂ 2 ♀, 21 km S. Windhoek, sandy wash in mountains 1 800 m, 31.I.1974, Irwin (N.M.); 1 ♂ 4 ♀, 25 km N.W. Omaruru, dry wash in *Acacia*-covered plain, 1 200 m, 5.II.1974, Irwin (N.M.);

Fig. 38. Lateral aspect of female genitalia of *Psilinus cinerascens*.

1 ♀, 50 km N.W. Omaruru, floodplain with large *Acacia* trees, 1 200 ft, 5.II.1974, Irwin (N.M.); 1 ♂ 3 ♀, Namib Desert Park, Kuiseb River at Gobabeb, riverine forest and sand, 400 m, 12.II.1974, Irwin (N.M.); 1 ♀, E. Caprivi, Katima Mulilo, 20–28.X.1970, Strydom (N.M.); 7 ♂ 21 ♀, Popa Falls, Kavango 26–31.VIII.1971, Channing, Penrith & Coetzee (S.M.); 6 ♂ 11 ♀, Andara, Kavango, 20–25.VIII.1971, Channing, Penrith & Coetzee (S.M.); 4 ♂ 6 ♀, Huab 261, Outjo, 29.XI.1972, Coetzee (S.M.); 2 ♂ 2 ♀, Otjitambi 25, Outjo, 14–15.II.1972, Penrith (S.M.); 2 ♂ 8 ♀, Ondorusu Falls, Koakoland, 23–26.VIII.1973, Penrith, Kensley, Tebje & Batista (S.M.); 1 ♂ 1 ♀, Wasservallei (W), Windhoek, 20–23.XII.1974, Louw (S.M.); 1 ♀, Noachabeb 97, Keetmanshoop, 22–28.IV.1972, Penrith & Coetzee (S.M.); 1 ♀, Fish River Canyon, 16–22.VIII.1958, St Andrews College (A.M.); 5 ♂ 5 ♀, Zessfontein, II.1925, Mus. Exped. (S.A.M.); 1 ♂, Windhoek, XII.1919, Tucker (S.A.M.); 1 ♂ 1 ♀, Kaross, Mus. Exped. (S.A.M.); 2 ♂, Otjivarongo, II.1919, Tucker (S.A.M.); 2 ♀, Outjo, I.1925, Mus. Exped. (S.A.M.); 1 ♀, Warmbad, Koakoveld, II.1925, Mus. Exped. (S.A.M.). BOTSWANA: 2 ♀, Nata, at light, Holm, Jacobs, Kirsten & Scholtz (N.M.). RHODESIA: 2 ♀, Sawmills, 24.IX.1920 (N.M.R.); 1 ♀, same data, 12.IX.1920 (N.M.R.); 2 ♀, same data, 23.XI.1922 (N.M.R.); 1 ♀, same data, 23.X.1932 (N.M.R.); 1 ♀, same data, 12.XII.1926 (N.M.R.); 1 ♀, Matopos, 17.X.1920 (N.M.R.); 1 ♂, Matopos, no date (N.M.R.); 1 ♀, Bindura, IX.1939 (N.M.R.); 1 ♀, Alicevale Farm, Vumba, near Zimunya Research Stn. of Umtali, 27.XII.1977, Wheeler (N.M.R.); 1 ♀, 96 miles S.E. Nuanetsi, IV.1961 (N.M.R.); 1 ♀, Balla Balla, III.1931, Cuthbertson (P.P.R.I.); 1 ♂ 2 ♀ Nangunya Reserve, Urungwe, 14.IX.1938, Williams (P.P.R.I.); 1 ♀, On Bath, Wedza, 26.XII.1938, Cuthbertson (P.P.R.I.); 1 ♀, Hippo Pools, Hartley, 1.III.1935, Williams (P.P.R.I.); 1 ♂, Rekometjie Research Stn., 4.XII.1973, Phelps (University of Rhodesia); 1 ♀, Lusulu, 23.XI.1963, Simmonds (University of Rhodesia). MOZAMBIQUE: 2 ♀, Chinde, Zambezi River delta, Usher (N.M.); 1 ♀, Inhaca Isl., Lourenço Marques (Maputo), 26.XII.1972, De Moor (N.M.R.). ANGOLA: 2 ♂ 3 ♀, Maluila, 22–23.XI.1974, Penrith (S.M.).

Distribution: A widespread species; activity period summarised in Table 1. Oldroyd (1939) recorded the species from Kilembe (Ruwendzori) and Hull (1967) gives additional records from Lesotho. Bromley (1942) recorded the species from

Madagascar and although I have not seen his material I suspect that he may have had specimens of *S. parvulus*.

Stichopogon umkomaasensis Oldroyd, 1974 (Figs 3, 20, 24, 32)

Stichopogon umkomaasensis Oldroyd, 1974. *Ann. Natal Mus.* 22: 83-4.

Oldroyd (1974) gave only a very brief description of this species in his key to South African *Stichopogon*. His type series consisted of only two female specimens. I have since discovered two males and the following redescription is based on all four specimens.

Redescription: ♂: **Head:** Shape of eyes, face and vertex (Fig. 3) similar to *S. unicolor*. Antennae dark-brown, heavily silver-grey pruinose. Face, vertex and occipital region black but heavily-masked by dense silver-grey pruinescence. Mystax shiny-white. Ocelli shiny orange-brown. All setae of head silver-white.

Thorax: Blackish masked by dense silver-grey pruinescence. Mesonotum possesses a shiny central longitudinal stripe and two black spots on either side of this stripe (well illustrated by Oldroyd, 1974). Wing membrane hyaline and iridescent. Veins light yellow-brown. Haltere light-yellow with slightly darker base. Legs: Coxae, trochanters, femora and proximal parts of tibiae dark red-brown covered with dense silver-grey pruinescence. Tarsal segments and distal end of tibiae yellow-brown, thinly silver pruinose. All setae and bristles shiny silver-grey. Claws dark-brown with yellow-brown base. Empodium orange-brown. Pulvilli light yellow-brown.

Abdomen: Blackish, masked by a uniformly dense silver-grey pruinescence. No distinctive pattern although the pruinescence may take on a darker appearance depending on the angles of illumination and viewing (see ♀ for illustration). ♂ genitalia as in Fig. 24. Epandrium shortish and without well-developed posterolateral lobes. Gonopods short with undulating upper margin (in lateral view) and a well-developed flat flange which juts out distally partly obscuring the style. This flange bears about five ventrally-directed setae. Style strongly upturned distally as in *S. caffer* and *S. unicolor*.

♀: General description as for male. ♀ genitalia as in Fig. 32. Subgenital plate bears a tuft of gold setae subapically, the tip of the plate being unobscured by the tuft.

Figs 39-40. Lateral aspect of *Clinopogon nicobarensis* genitalia. 39. Male. 40. Female.

Abdominal pattern as in Fig. 20 (see comments under ♂).

Material examined: SOUTH AFRICA: *Natal:* 2 ♀, holotype and paratype, Umkomaas beach, 9.XII.1954, Stuckenberg (N.M.). *TRANSKEI:* 2 ♂, 50 km S.E. Bizana, coastal, 17.II.1973, Irwin (N.M.).

Distribution: The two localities at which specimens have been collected indicate that this species occurs on the beaches of Natal and Transkei. It is probable that the species also occurs along the coasts of the eastern Cape Province and Mozambique. Activity period is summarised in Table 1.

Remarks: This is a very characteristic species having close similarities with *S. unicolor* and to a lesser extent *S. caffer* and *S. irwini*.

Stichopogon unicolor Ricardo, 1925 (Figs 4, 21, 25, 33)

Stichopogon unicolor Ricardo, 1925. *Ann. Mag. nat. Hist.* (9)15: 276.

Redescription: ♂: *Head:* Shape of eyes, face and vertex (Fig. 4) similar to *S. umkomaasensis*, the vertex not being so strongly divergent as in other species of *Stichopogon*. Antennae black, silver pruinose. Face blackish covered with silver pruinescence. Mystax silver-white. Vertex black with sparse silver and gold pruinescence. Occiput black, densely silver pruinose, bristles black, setae silver-white.

Thorax: Black, uniformly covered with silver pruinescence laterally. Dorsally black with fine silver and gold pruinescence. Setae: 1 presutural, 1 supra-alar, 1 postalar, all black. Wing membrane hyaline and iridescent, veins dark-brown except for bases of main veins which are yellow-brown. Legs: uniformly black, silver-grey pruinose, setae and bristles shiny-silver. Claws dark-brown with light brown base. Empodium yellow-brown. Pulvilli light yellow-brown.

Abdomen: Shiny dark brown-black with a pattern of silver-grey pruinescence similar to ♀. ♂ genitalia as in Fig. 25. Epandrium shortish with moderately well-developed postero-lateral lobes. Proctigal comb composed of four spines only. Gonopods similar to *S. umkomaasensis* but distal flange not as well-developed and only obscuring a small part of the style (in lateral view).

♀: similar to ♂. ♀ genitalia as in Fig. 33. Subgenital plate bears tuft of gold setae subapically such that the tip is not obscured. Abdominal pattern as in Fig. 21.

Material examined: SOUTH AFRICA: *Cape Province:* 8 ♂ 2 ♀, 2 miles S.W. Brandkop, stream bed, 1 300 ft, 12.IX.1972, Irwin (N.M.); 1 ♀, E. of Pakhuis Pass, IX.1947, Mus. Exped. (S.A.M.); 1 ♂, Droë Rivier, Namaqualand, 30.IX.1966 (S.A.M.); 10 ♂ 9 ♀, 10 km E. Rhodes, rocky stream banks, 9.I.1979, Londt & Stuckenberg (N.M.); 7 ♂ 7 ♀, Rhodes, rocky stream banks, 10–11.I.1979, Londt & Stuckenberg (N.M.); 1 ♂, 7 kms S. Swellendam, Bontebok National Park, ex. malaise trap near river, III.1979, Braack (N.M.). RHODESIA: 2 ♀, Bulawayo, 17.VI.1923, Stevenson (N.M.); 2 ♀ Matopos, 9.VIII.1924 (N.M.R.); 2 ♂, Bulawayo, 2.IX.1922, Rhodesian Mus. (S.A.M.).

Distribution: Known only from the Cape Province and Rhodesia (Bulawayo area). I have seen males from Rhodesia and there is no doubt that they are identical to males from the Cape. Seasonal incidence is summarised in Table 1.

BIOLOGICAL NOTES ON STICHOPOGON

Efflatoun (1937), working on North African *Stichopogon*, stated that 'all the species are known to occur on sand, on sandy river banks, sand shores of lakes and Seas as well as on dry quicksand'. This statement was supported by Cuthbertson (1938) and Engel & Cuthbertson (1939) in respect of their observations on *S. punctum* and *S. maculipennis* (= *S. hermanni*). My own experience collecting at many localities in southern Africa adds further support to this statement. Many of the specimens listed in this paper are accompanied by brief notes on collecting conditions and while some of these support Efflatoun's statement a number of specimens have been collected in dry sandy river beds or along the stony banks of mountain streams (*S. unicolor*). Many of the rivers in South West Africa flow for only a very brief period annually but often possess semi-permanent pools of water, sometimes very deep, or have damp soil immediately under the dry upper layers of the river bed. In Madagascar specimens were collected in sandy areas not adjacent to streams but as these localities were in a very high rainfall area dampness of the ground was assured. A plot of all the localities where *Stichopogon* have been collected in southern Africa is given in Fig. 41. The apparent absence of these flies from the central region may be as a result of the absence of even semi-permanent rivers. The possibility of collecting bias must, however, not be ignored.

Why *Stichopogon*, and probably all Stichopogonini, require damp sandy conditions is not known. No data are available on the life cycle of any of the species and prey records are very limited (nymphal Acrididae, nymphal Dictyopharidae and adult Diptera of the families Anthomyiidae, Lauxaniidae, Ephydriidae and Tachinidae) so no valuable clues can be gleaned from these sources. Casual observations suggest that these highly cryptic flies rest on sandy soil unnoticed by their prey and feed on any insects which happen to be hopping or flying around in their vicinity. The female *Stichopogon* is equipped with acanthopores and can thus be expected to oviposit in the soil. Damp soil may be a requisite for the developing larvae.

Genus *Sporadothrix* Hermann, 1907

The single species of *Sporadothrix*, *S. gracilis* Hermann, 1907, is not known to me. Hermann's type specimen (from the Kalahari Desert) was badly damaged. Oldroyd (1974) felt reasonably confident that he had found a single intact male specimen from South West Africa belonging to this genus. *Sporadothrix*, which in some ways is related to *Anypodetus*, is characterised by graceful, elongate tarsi ending in almost straight, very slender, claws. Pulvilli are entirely absent. Oldroyd (1974) gives an illustration of the South West African specimen and assigns it to *S. gracilis* Hermann. Judging from this illustration I would agree with him.

Genus *Psilinus* Wulp, 1899

Like *Sporadothrix* this genus is monotypic. Wulp described *P. cinerascens* from material collected at Aden and now thought to be preserved at the Hope Museum, Oxford. Hull (1962) examined these specimens and gave a detailed description of the genus and a number of good illustrations. I have seen a single

female from Kenya which I feel belongs to this genus and most probably this species. Wulp (1899) states that his specimens lack pulvilli while Hull (1967) failed to record the nature of these structures. Oldroyd (1963), however, uses the development of the pulvilli in his key to the genera of African Asilidae so I presume he had seen the type specimens. He characterised *Psilinus* as having pulvilli reduced to narrow vestiges. The female from Kenya answers this description perfectly. Oldroyd (1963) states that the eyes are separated at the vertex by only about twice the width of the ocellar tubercle. Hull's (1962) illustration of the head shows a greater separation of at least three times the width of the ocellar tubercle. The Kenyan specimen agrees with Hull's illustration. It is therefore with some hesitation that I place this interesting specimen under the name *P. cinerascens*.

Psilinus cinerascens Wulp, 1899 (Figs 1, 5, 38)

Psilinus cinerascens Wulp, 1899. *Trans.Ent. Soc. Lond.* 1899: 85.

Redescription: ♀: **Head:** Shape of eyes, face and vertex as in Fig. 5. Antennae orange-brown and of typical *Stichopogon* structure. Face shiny-silver pruinose with a few moderately well-developed yellow setae centrally. Mystax shiny-yellow. Vertex blackish but well masked by orange-gold pruinescence. Occipital region mainly silver-grey pruinose ventrally and gold dorsally. Occipital and vertical bristles light-yellow.

Fig. 41. The distribution of *Stichopogon* in southern Africa.

Thorax: Brown, with silver and gold pruinescence laterally and matt-gold pruinescence dorsally. Very few setae evident. Setae: 1 presutural, 1 supra-alar, 1 postalar, all yellow-brown. Wing membranes hyaline and iridescent, venation as in *Stichopogon*. Legs: Uniformly orange-brown, silver-gold pruinose, setae and bristles shiny light-yellow. Claws blackish with orange-brown base; empodium shiny light-yellow; pulvilli (Fig. 1) one-third the length of claws, light-yellow. Postmetacoxal area entirely membranous.

Abdomen: Light red-brown; lateral margins silver-gold pruinose. ♀ genitalia (Fig. 38) similar to *Stichopogon unicolor* and *S. umkomaasensis* in that the subgenital plate has a tuft of gold setae subapically.

Material examined: KENYA: 1 ♀, Archers Post, 15.I.1973, Bampton (N.M.).

Remarks: Efflatoun (1937) described *Stichopogon flaviventris* from two males and five females collected at Gebel Elba (South Eastern Desert, Egypt) and El Arish (Northern Sinai). This species, described as remarkable and possessing characters 'worthy almost of generic rank', appears to be congeneric with *Psilinus*. Efflatoun (1937) described the pretarsus as follows: 'Claws conspicuously black (owing to the pale colour of the legs) and unusually long and straight (i.e. only very feebly bent); pulvilli and empodium microscopic, vestigial and may be termed absent.' This description suggests that *S. flaviventris* and *P. cinerascens* belong to the same genus. Certainly the localities of all the relevant material support this suggestion. The illustration given by Efflatoun (1937) of the female subgenital plate (his Fig. 267) indicates the complete absence of the two groups of gold setae present in the Kenyan specimen (Fig. 38). I therefore suggest that *cinerascens* and *flaviventris* should be considered sister species within the same genus. Whether this genus should be *Stichopogon*, *Psilinus* or a yet to be described new genus based on the development of the pulvilli can only be decided after a detailed comparison of all the relevant material. For the present I shall assume that Oldroyd (1963) did study the type of *Psilinus* and that the vestigial nature of the pulvilli is an adequate character defining the genus *Psilinus* to which both the above species should be assigned.

Genus *Clinopogon* Bezzi, 1910

This entirely littoral genus has been discussed by Oldroyd (1959, 1972, 1974). All the material available to me suggests that Oldroyd (1974) was correct when he expressed doubt as to the validity of *C. grossus* (Bromley). I have seen the types of this species and three other specimens from southern African beaches and these are identical in morphology to specimens from Mauritius and Madagascar. I therefore recognise only a single *Clinopogon* from the Afrotropical Region.

Clinopogon nicobarensis (Schiner, 1868) (Figs 39–40)

Stichopogon nicobarensis Schiner, 1868. *Novara Reise Zool.* II. Diptera p. 161.

Clinopogon nicobarensis; Oldroyd, 1959. *Mém. l'Inst. Sci. Mad* 11: 269.

Stichopogon grossus Bromley, 1947. *Ann. Durban Mus.* 3: 112 syn. n.

Clinopogon grossus; Oldroyd, 1974. *Ann. Natal Mus.* 22: 80–81.

Redescription: ♂: *Head*: Shape of eyes, face and vertex generally similar to *Stichopogon* species. Entire head blackish with silver-grey pruinescence. Mystax

silver-white and more extensive than in *Stichopogon* species. Antennae blackish with silver-grey pruinescence. Vertex covered with fine not very dense silver-grey setae. Occipital and vertical setae pale-white. Long shiny silver-grey setae on lower occiput. Palpi and rostrum dark red-brown.

Thorax: Black, heavily masked by silver-grey pruinescence. Setae: 1 presutural, 1 supra-alar, 1 postalar (although smaller subsidiary setae may be present) all light-yellow. Wing membrane semi-hyaline with a light-grey appearance. Fourth posterior cell without a basal stalk (as illustrated by Oldroyd, 1974). Legs: uniformly black, silver-grey pruinose, bearing silver setae and shiny yellow-white bristles.

Abdomen: Black, masked by silver-grey pruinescence, covered with short silver setae. ♂ genitalia as in Fig. 39. Epandrium short; proctiger long, jutting out well beyond end of epandrium. Style well-developed, highly moveable with a sharp upwardly pointing apex.

♀: Similar to ♂. Subgenital plate clearly split down the centre and not bearing tufts of gold setae as in most *Stichopogon* species (Fig. 40).

Material examined: MADAGASCAR: 4 ♀, Sainte-Luce, 10 m dct. Fort Dauphin, 22-24.II.1958, Stuckenberg (N.M.); 1 ♂, Fenerive, on beach, XII.1955, Stuckenberg. MAURITIUS: 1 ♂ 2 ♀, Albatross Island, St Brandon, 29.IV.1967, Courtois (N.M.); 2 ♀, St Brandon, Raphaël, 28.IV.1967, Courtois (N.M.); 1 ♂, Palmer, 14.III.1939, with prey - Heteroptera Veliidae, Courtois (N.M.). SOUTH AFRICA: Natal: 1 ♀, Blythdale Beach (Stanger), 25.II.1963, Schofield (N.M.); 1 ♀, Mtunzini, 7.II.1965, Schofield (N.M.); 1 ♀, Tugela River Mouth, 9.III.1962, Schofield (N.M.); 1 ♂ (holotype of *S. grossus*), Durban, Bell-Marley (D.M.); 1 ♀ (allotype of *S. grossus*), Bluff Durban, 27.III.1920, Barker (D.M.).

Distribution: The Afrotropical distribution of *C. nicobarensis* appears to be confined to the eastern beaches of the African mainland, Madagascar and the Indian Ocean Islands. I have not seen specimens of *C. sauteri* Bezzi which has been recorded from Egypt (Efflatoun, 1937), but there is a possibility that these Egyptian records refer to *C. nicobarensis* as *C. sauteri* was originally described from Rakao, Formosa. Certainly the description given by Efflatoun (1937) could quite easily pertain to *C. nicobarensis*.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I thank Mr F. W. Gess (Albany Museum), Dr M-L. Penrith (State Museum), Mr C. Quickelberge (Durban Museum), Dr V. Whitehead (South African Museum), Mr W. Mitchell (Plant Protection Research Inst., Salisbury) and Mrs C. Car (National Museum, Bulawayo) for their assistance with the loan of specimens and Dr B. R. Stuckenberg (Natal Museum) for critically reading the manuscript and for encouragement. I am indebted to the Council for Scientific and Industrial Research for a grant towards this project.

REFERENCES

- BROMLEY, S. W., 1942. Madagascar robber flies with descriptions of new species (Diptera: Asilidae). *Trans. Amer. Ent. Soc.* **68**: 11-21.
- CUTHBERTSON, A., 1938. Biological notes on some Diptera in Southern Rhodesia. *Trans. Rhod. Sci. Ass.* **36**: 115-132.
- EFFLATOUN, BEY, H. C. 1937. A monograph of Egyptian Diptera Part V. Family Asilidae (Section II). *Mém. Soc. Roy. Ent. D'Egypte.* **4**(3): 199-443.
- ENGEL, E. O. & CUTHBERTSON, A., 1939. Systematic and biological notes on some brachycerous Diptera of southern Rhodesia. *J. ent. Soc. sth. Afr.* **2**: 181-195.
- HULL, F. M., 1962. *Robber Flies of the World. The genera of the family Asilidae.* Smithsonian Institution, United States National Museum, Bulletin 224 (In 2 Parts).
- 1967. Diptera (Brachycera): Asilidae. *South African Animal Life* **13**: 234-283.
- OLDROYD, H., 1939. Rhagionidae, Tabanidae, Asilidae, Bombyliidae. Ruwenzori Expedition 1934-35. *British Mus. Nat. Hist.* **2**: 13-47.
- 1959. Synopsis des Asilidae (Diptera) de Madagascar. I. Tribus des Sarapogonini, Stichopogonini, Xenomyzini et Laphriini. *Mém. Inst. Sci. Madagascar.* Tananarive. **II**: 247-289.
- 1963. The tribes and genera of the African Asilidae (Diptera). *Stuttgarter Beitr. zur Naturk.* **107**: 1-16.
- 1972. Robber Flies (Diptera: Asilidae) of the Philippine Islands. *Pacific Insects* **14**(2): 201-337.
- 1974. An introduction to the Robber Flies (Diptera: Asilidae) of southern Africa. *Ann. Natal Mus.* **22**: 1-171.
- PAPAVERO, N., 1973. Studies of Asilidae (Diptera) Systematics and Evolution. I. A preliminary classification in subfamilies. *Arg. Zool., S. Paulo* **23**(3): 217-274.
- WULP, F. M. VAN DER, 1899. Asilidae from Aden and its neighbourhood. *Trans. Ent. Soc. Lond.* **1899**: 81-98.

Date received: 30 October 1978